

HEP Analysis workloads for the benchmarking suite

March 2021

AUTHOR(S):

Dominika Kankowska
Gdansk University of Technology, Intel AI

SUPERVISORS:

Xavier Valls Pla
CERN

Domenico Giordano
CERN

ABSTRACT

CERN measures computing systems' performance based on typical usage patterns that happen "in real life". Lately, the WLCG has started to move towards field-specific benchmarks, which by design, describe a particular system's performance more accurately. By benchmarking a system with workloads similar to the ones which are supposed to be run on it, we can estimate this system's performance more reliably. One of the typical computing patterns is the analysis of High Energy Physics (HEP) data.

We contribute a set of HEP analysis workloads to the Benchmarking Working Group's (BWG) benchmarking suite with this project. These workloads can be used to describe a system's performance for the task of running typical HEP analyses. Example analyses already exist in the context of the main analysis software of high energy physics, ROOT [7], for instance, leveraging CERN's open data.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	5
<hr/>	
HEP BENCHMARKS PROJECT	6
<hr/>	
SOFTWARE OVERVIEW	7
ROOT	
ROOTBENCH	
DOCKER	
SINGULARITY	
<hr/>	
IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS	8
SOLUTION	
HEP ANALYSIS WORKLOADS REPOSITORY STRUCTURE	
INTERFACE	
STEPS PERFORMED IN A CONTAINER	
RESULTS	
<hr/>	
CONCLUSION	9
FUTURE WORK	
<hr/>	
REFERENCES	10

1. INTRODUCTION

Lately, the WLCG Collaboration has started to move towards field-specific benchmarks (Figure 1). Before this change, CPU benchmarks such as HS06 [4] were used by WLCG to describe hardware systems' performance. All these benchmarks provide, as a result, a "score" metric. This metric is used to describe, for example, a CPU's performance in terms of accomplishing some HEP computations [1]. By benchmarking CPUs using workloads similar to the ones that are going to be run on them, in the WLCG case HEP workloads, we assure by construction that:

- a score calculated by the benchmark has a high correlation to the throughput of HEP workloads [1]
- a CPU usage pattern is similar to that of HEP workloads [1]

Figure 1. Scheme illustrating the change of benchmarks being used to measure the system's performance.

2. HEP BENCHMARKS PROJECT

We have contributed to the HEP Benchmarks project by including a set of analysis workloads, i.e. a selected group of algorithms that run on pre-reconstructed data, and apply statistical methods and kinematic filters to measure particle physics phenomena. This selection of algorithms is a part of one of the components of the HEP Benchmarks project. The HEP Benchmarks project consists of three components:

- HEP Benchmark Suite: automates the execution of multiple benchmarks, such as HEPsScore, SPEC CPU2017, HS06
- HEPsScore: orchestrates High Energy Physics workloads, computes and reports a single value summary score used to describe the system's performance
- HEP Workloads and HEP Workloads GPU: projects providing individual HEP Workloads

During this work, we wanted to contribute to the Benchmarking Working Group's benchmarking suite a set of analysis workloads by adding another project providing individual HEP Workloads: HEP Analysis Workloads.

3. SOFTWARE OVERVIEW

a. ROOT

ROOT is an important analysis framework in the world of High Energy Physics. It is the official LHC analysis framework used by all LHC experiments.

b. rootbench

Rootbench is a benchmarking project containing a set of small programs built on top of ROOT. It can run on several architectures such as ARM, PowerPC or x86 and its primary goal is to provide metrics to track performance over time. As a result of a benchmark's execution, rootbench generates a CSV file containing information such as the benchmark's name and its duration (Figure 2).

c. Docker

Docker is an open platform allowing packaging and running an application in an isolated environment called a container. By using a container, we can separate the application from the system [2]. Moreover, the container may store all of the application's dependencies, making software deployment easier.

d. Singularity

Singularity, similarly to Docker, is a container platform allowing creating and running a container storing an application and its dependencies in an isolated environment. Singularity allows importing a Docker image without having Docker installed or being a superuser. [3] The main differences between Docker and Singularity:

- No user contextual changes or root escalation allowed [3]
- No root-owned daemon processes [3]

4. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

In this section, we discuss the details of the implementation and collected results.

a. Solution

We prepared a Docker container based on Centos 7. The container stores several tools necessary for running analysis workloads:

- ROOT's and rootbench's dependencies
- ROOT and rootbench (compiled during the process of building the container)
- Prefetched input files needed to run workloads
- HEP Analysis Workloads repository

During the container's build, we prefetch all the necessary files for the benchmarks' execution. The host running the container may not be connected to the network, so all of the necessary data must be stored locally in the container.

We use rootbench to run analysis workloads. As a result, rootbench saves a CSV output file containing details of the workload's execution (Figure 2). The metric we describe the system's performance with is the duration time of the benchmark. In Figure 2, we can see this metric under the `cpu_time` field of the CSV file.


```

2020-08-27 12:36:53
Running /hep-analysis-workloads/build_rootbench/build/root/roofit/vectorisedPDFs/benchAddPdf
Run on (64 X 3000 MHz CPU s)
CPU Caches:
  L1 Data 32K (x32)
  L1 Instruction 32K (x32)
  L2 Unified 512K (x32)
  L3 Unified 16384K (x16)
Load Average: 2.04, 1.10, 0.47
***WARNING*** CPU scaling is enabled, the benchmark real time measurements may be noisy and will incur extra overhead.
name,iterations,real_time,cpu_time,time_unit,bytes_per_second,items_per_second,label,error_occurred,error_message
"benchAddPdfGaussExp/0",1,1212.49,1212,ms,,,,,
"benchAddPdfGaussExp/1",1,22206.4,22204.1,ms,,,,,
"benchAddPdfGaussExp/2",1,1285.47,1284.94,ms,,,,,
"benchAddPdfGaussExp/3",1,25066,25063.4,ms,,,,,
"benchAddPdfGaussExp/4",1,2217.73,2216.8,ms,,,,,
"benchAddPdfGaussExp/5",1,28777.5,28774.5,ms,,,,,

```

Figure 2. Content of the example CSV file saved by rootbench.

Rootbench provides a considerable number of CPU benchmarks, but only a subset of them is relevant for measuring a system's CPU performance. The ROOT team curated the following list of CPU benchmarks run by our solution:

- RDataFrame benchmarks
 - ROOT tutorials: df101 to df106 - realistic analysis benchmarks using open data
 - CERN Open Data HTT analysis - realistic analysis example with multiple steps (skimming, making histograms, plotting)
- RooFit benchmarks

There are two requirements for the prepared solution to be added to the benchmarking suite. First, the solution must compute a single value score to summarize the system's performance while running the analysis workloads. This score is calculated as a weighted sum of the execution times of each benchmark. The weights used in the weighted sum are stored in the benchmark.txt file (see Figure 3). This file contains two columns: the first column contains the names of the benchmarks, which should be run, and the second one shows the weight assigned to the duration of this benchmark. Currently, we assign weight 1 to each of the benchmarks. These weights will be fine-tuned by the BWG to describe systems' performance more accurately.

```

1  RDataFrameh1Analysis 1
2  gbenchmark-df102 1
3  gbenchmark-df103 1
4  pytest-df104 1
5  benchAddPdf 1
6  wmassAnalysis 1

```

Figure 3. Contents of the benchmark.txt file.

The second requirement is to generate a JSON summary file that contains detailed output for each benchmark. The example of a simplified summary file is shown in Figure 3.

We automated the process of Docker container build by using GitLab's continuous integration (CI). We prepared several CI jobs:

- Build Docker image containing ROOT
- Build Docker image containing rootbench
- Build a standalone Docker image
- Run container using Docker
- Run container using Singularity

The first three jobs are focusing on building a standalone Docker container in three steps. In the first step, we prepare a container with only ROOT dependencies and compiled ROOT. In the second step, we add rootbench dependencies and compile rootbench. Lastly, we prefetch the necessary files and set the container's entry point.

Then, we define two jobs used to test running the built container with both Docker and Singularity. When running a container with Singularity, we use the same Docker container, which will be converted while running it with Singularity. For both of these jobs, we save the JSON summary file as a CI artifact.

```
{
  "wl-scores": "280.300233127981",
  "wl-stats": {
    "RDataFrame1Analysis": {
      "BM_RDataFrame_h1Analysis/repeats:1": {
        "cpu_time": "4090800000.0",
        "duration": "4141030000.0",
        "unit": "ns",
        "status": "passed"
      },
      "BM_RDataFrame_h1Analysis_MT/8/repeats:1": {
        "cpu_time": "1933160000.0",
        "duration": "1938120000.0",
        "unit": "ns",
        "status": "passed"
      }
    }
  },
  "log": "passed"
}
```

Figure 4. Example content of the JSON summary file generated by our solution.

b. HEP Analysis Workloads repository structure

In Figure 5, we can see a scheme illustrating the structure of the HEP Analysis Workloads repository. Here is a short introduction of prepared files:

- .gitlab-ci.yml and root-ci.yml
 - YAML files describing the Gitlab CI jobs
- Dockerfile.root, Dockerfile.rootbench and Dockerfile.standalone
 - files containing commands which are being run during three stages of container build
- root_frozen_commit.txt and rootbench_frozen_commit.txt
 - files specifying which commit of the ROOT's and rootbench's repositories should be used while compiling these tools

- benchmarks.txt
 - file used for choosing which benchmarks to run and which weights should be assigned to them while calculating the score of the workload
- parseSummary.py
 - script used to find CSV log files generated by rootbench and parse them. While parsing a CSV file, this script gathers information such as the name of the benchmark for which a specific log file was generated, the status of the benchmark (passed/failed) and, if the benchmark has passed, its duration time
- generateSummary.py
 - script used to generate a JSON summary file based on data gathered by parseResults.py

Figure 5. Structure of the HEP Analysis Workloads repository.

c. Interface

To run the standalone container using Docker, we need to issue the command:

```
docker run gitlab-registry.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-analysis-workloads
```

The benchmarks' results, saved in the format expected by the HEP Benchmarks project, can be found in the container's /results folder. If we want to access them from outside the container, we need to bind-mount a local directory in /results:

```
docker run -v <local_dir>:/results gitlab-registry.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-analysis-workloads
```

To run the same container using Singularity, we need to issue the command:

```
singularity run -C --writable-tmpfs -B <local_dir>:/results \
docker://gitlab-registry.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-analysis-workloads
```

In our solution, we didn't prepare any separate image specifically for running it with Singularity. Instead, we decided to use the same Docker image, which is being converted during the run of the command shown above. The most significant difference between the commands used when running the container with Docker and Singularity is using the `--writable-tmpfs` option in the latter case. During its execution, rootbench saves log files in the container. Singularity runs the container with a read-only filesystem, which prohibits rootbench from saving files necessary to generate a JSON summary. As a solution, we decided to use the `--writable-tmpfs` option, which allows saving small files.

d. Steps performed in a container

In this section, we discuss the steps performed in a container after running it using one of the commands listed in the Interface section. The container's entry point is the `run.sh` script. This script performs a series of tasks to run benchmarks and gather the results:

- Reading the `benchmarks.txt` file describing which benchmarks to run and the weights assigned to them
- Running rootbench using the following command for each of the benchmarks specified in the `benchmarks.txt` file:

```
ctest -R <name of the benchmark> -VV, for example:
```

```
ctest -R gbenchmark-df102 -VV
```

- Running `parseResults.py` to parse the CSV files generated by rootbench, with the details of each benchmark's execution
- Running `generateSummary.py` to generate and save a JSON summary file containing:
 - benchmarks' names and their durations
 - status of each benchmark (passed/failed)
 - single value score of the workload

e. Results

To test the CPU execution time of the whole workload consisting of six benchmarks, we ran the container on a dual-socket 64-core(128 SMT) AMD EPYC 7702 (2.0GHz, up to 3.35GHz) node. The average execution time, calculated based on five runs of the workload, is 303.87 seconds, with the whole process running for around 5 minutes. The length of benchmarks is tunable by increasing the size of the input data. Moreover, we have identified some areas which could be useful to improve the quality of our workload:

- Some of the benchmarks we would like to run are not available in rootbench yet (for example, GPU benchmarks)
- Multithreaded benchmarks (around 50% of the total number of benchmarks run during the workload's execution) are fixed to use only eight threads. It means that the node is not being utilized fully. We would like the number of used threads to be parameterizable in the future.

5. CONCLUSION

To conclude, during this work, we were able to prepare a HEP Analysis Workloads project. The prepared workload can describe a system's performance for the task of running typical analyses.

a. Future work

We identified several possible future tasks which could further improve the quality of the prepared solution:

- Integration of the solution into HEP Benchmark Suite
- Addition of TMVA (CPU and GPU) benchmarks when available in rootbench
- Tuning of the single workload score calculation. Currently, all the weights used to calculate a single value score are equal to 1. These values should be tuned to allow for more accurate benchmarking of the system
- When we are running the Docker container using Singularity, the container runs with a read-only filesystem. We encountered an issue while running rootbench with Singularity, which is related to a lack of ability to save the generated log files. There is no possibility to choose where rootbench should save the logs, so bind-mounting a writable directory doesn't solve this issue. We decided to fix it by using the `--writable-tmpfs` option in a command running the container using Singularity, but in the future, we would prefer to have an option to choose where the log files should be saved
- Parameterization of the number of parallel processing units

6. REFERENCES

- [1] HEP benchmarks for CPUs and beyond:
<https://indico.cern.ch/event/908146/contributions/3826766/subcontributions/305948/attachments/2033812/3412612/HSF-WLCG-Workshop-13-05-2020-giordano.pdf>
- [2] Docker overview:
<https://docs.docker.com/get-started/overview/>
- [3] Singularity:
<https://singularity.lbl.gov/>
- [4] Using HEP experiment workflows for the benchmarking and accounting of WLCG computing resources:
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2004.01609>
- [5] Next Generation of HEP CPU Benchmarks:
https://www.epj-conferences.org/articles/epjconf/abs/2019/19/epjconf_chep2018_08011/epjconf_chep2018_08011.html
- [6] HEP Analysis Workloads repository:
<https://gitlab.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-analysis-workloads>
- [7] ROOT repository:
<https://github.com/root-project/root>
- [8] ROOT overview:
<http://xvallspl.github.io/blog/cern/root/>
- [9] rootbench repository:
<https://github.com/root-project/rootbench>

